

Tsallis Entropy is No Longer Linked Maximum Probability if $q \neq 1$? Part 2

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In Part I, we noted that usual maximization of probability Product over i p_i power $(N p_i)$ which yields Shannon's entropy does not apply to the Tsallis case. We then asked: What is maximized in the Tsallis scenario? This is the question we wish to investigate here.

We first note that Tsallis entropy is linked with a physical probability p_i power q , where Sum over i $p(i) = 1$. In other words, if a probability should be maximized, one would assume that it is $p(i)$ because this is the normalized probability. This, however, would be the usual Shannon maximization, usually with respect to the constraint Sum over i $e_i p_i = E_{total}$. In the Tsallis case, the constraint is now associated with p_i power q and p_i , i.e. Sum over i $e_i p_i$ power $q = E$. As a result, it seems that one cannot maximize a Shannon's entropy expression, although in the case of $q=1$, the Shannon result should appear because then the a priori constraint Sum over $e_i p_i = E$ holds.

Furthermore, given that p_i power q appears in the constraint, it seems that one should apply the same ideas that are applied in the Shannon case to the p_i power q case, as argued in Part I, i.e. p_i power q is the probability for i , then an overall probability of N trials: Product over $i=1, N$ $\{p_i$ power $q\}$ power $\{N p_i$ power $q\}$ does not lead to Tsallis entropy, even though it yields Shannon's entropy for $q=1$. Thus, we argued in Part I, that the Tsallis approach does not maximize probability to the fullest, i.e. does not minimize information to the fullest. We, however, asked: Then what is being maximized?

We suggest that regardless of the distribution of p_i , Sum over i $p_i = 1$ holds. If $p_i \rightarrow p_i$ power q , then sum over i p_i power $q < 1$ (for all $p_i < 1$). This is an expression which mimics the a priori physical constraint: Sum over i $e_i p_i$ power q , just as in the Shannon's case. Thus, extremizing an expression of the form Sum over i p_i power q could lead to the Shannon's case as $q \rightarrow 1 + \delta$, if one converts Sum over i p_i power q to $\{\text{Sum over } i p_i \text{ power } q - 1\} / \{1 - q\}$. A priori, however, one is no longer maximizing overall probability as a fundamental principle. Rather, one considers that instead of Sum over i p_i , one has sum over i p_i power q as a natural probability sum linked to the constraint. It is, however, not simply a matter of maximizing this expression, because the $q=1$ case must account for Shannon's entropy as a global maximization of probability.

As a result, it seems that in the Tsallis $q \neq 1$ case, one does not worry about maximization of global probability (minimal information), but only extremizes a function closely linked to the constraint such that $q=1$ yields Shannon's entropy. In other words, to a large degree one extremizes a probability (p_i power q) which is similar to that in the e_i constraint. In the $q=1$ case, p_i is the probability in the e_i constraint and so p_i should appear in the entropy expression, and it does, but it is multiplied by $\ln(p_i)$ (information) such that $p_i \ln(p_i) = \ln(p_i \text{ power } p_i) \approx -? \ln(n_i \text{ power } n_i) \approx -\ln(n!)$. This in turn is linked with a maximum number of arrangements, i.e. minimal information. Thus, Tsallis entropy seems to be created by focusing on the $q=1$ case being the only one which really minimizes information and deliberately gains information for $q \neq 1$. Thus, non-minimal information states are suggested to exist in nature, with extra

information not being due to a priori constraints, but to the Tsallis scheme of formulating a power function which only yields maximum probability (minimal information) in the $q=1$ case.

Minimization of Information

Entropy considerations began with the notion of Boltzmann entropy which is equivalent to Shannon's entropy. Boltzmann entropy is $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$, so for a maximum number of states one has minimal information because there is a maximum number of states in which the system may lie. In the Shannon case, one has:

Probability (N trials) = Product over i p_i power $N p_i$ so

$$\ln(\text{Probability}(N)) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } N p_i \ln(p_i) \quad ((1))$$

where ((1)) is - Shannon's entropy.

Again, maximization of Probability(N) means a global minimum of information. Thus, it seems that the original Boltzmann-Shannon view of entropy is one of a global minimum in terms of information subject to any a priori constraints which might exist such as: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i = 1$ and $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p_i = 1$. In other words, this seems to have become an essential idea of statistical mechanics.

We suggest that Tsallis entropy does not respect this notion of global minimal information subject to a priori constraints. Rather, it respects it only for $q=1$, but for p_i power q , which is a physical probability which appears in nature, if $q \neq 1$, one does not need to have a global information minimum.

((2)) The constraint is that a global information constraint only needs to hold for $q=1$.

If one is willing to accept ((2)) (i.e. if this is how nature behaves), one may develop Tsallis entropy. We wish to point out, however, that one breaks away from the notion of minimal information subject to a priori constraints (as also noted in Part I).

As noted in Part I, the expression for global minimal information for p_i power q would be:

$$\ln(\text{Probability}) = \text{sum over } i \text{ } \{N p_i \text{ power } q\} \ln(p_i) \quad ((3))$$

The Tsallis Scenario

We have argued in previous notes that the Tsallis scenario hinges on the existence of a physical probability of the form:

$$p_i \text{ power } q \quad ((4))$$

We have previously cited the example of p_i representing the probability that a sunflower seed is not eaten by a bird in a day, but germination requires q days. One cannot simply call p_i power q the new probability because it is not normalized to 1, whereas $\sum_i p_i = 1$.

One may ask then: Even in the case of p_i power q , why does one not extremize p_i , subject to a priori constraints? The answer seems to be that the a priori constraints are not associated with p_i , but with p_i power q :

$$\text{Constraint } \sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((5))$$

In other words, one might at first consider maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to ((5)) instead of $\sum_i p_i$. In the case of $q=1$, one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution while in the case $q \neq 1$, one would not. The problem with this argument is that Shannon's entropy arises from taking \ln of Probability(N) = Product over i p_i power $N p_i$. Thus, for p_i power q , one should use ((3)). If one does not use ((3)), as in the case of Tsallis entropy, one does not minimize information globally.

The purpose of this note is to try to understand what is being extremized in the Tsallis case. The fact that $q=1$ yields Shannon's entropy is not special follows from extremizing ((3)) subject to ((5)), which also yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for $q=1$ and ((3)) is Shannon's entropy for $q=1$. The Tsallis prescription is deliberately something different from minimizing global information.

The Tsallis prescription is one in which minimal global information only exists for $q=1$ and more information seems to creep in (on purpose) as q increases from 1. This is a very different idea from the usual maximization of probability (minimization of information) usually associated with statistical mechanics. The question then seems to be: Why does the Tsallis approach allow for more than minimal information for $q>1$? Why is it that only when q relaxes to 1, that one has minimal information?

The answer may be linked to the idea that for p_i normalized, i.e. $\sum_i p_i = 1$, p_i power q , physical as it is, is not normalized. The maximization of information (Shannon's entropy) seems to be linked with a single normalized probability. If two probabilities exist p_i and p_i power q and only one can be normalized, i.e. p_i , then it is possible that the usual maximization of probability (minimization of information) no longer holds unless one moves to the $q=1$ limit in which case one has p_i , the normalized probability.

If this is the case, then Tsallis entropy seems to introduce a new idea into statistical mechanics, namely that one does not always maximize entropy (minimize information) subject to a priori constraints. This only occurs if one has a probability which may be a priori normalized. Creating a second probability from a first one which is normalized leads to an unnormalized probability and does not require maximum probability (minimal information) according to the Tsallis scheme.

The Tsallis Scheme

The Tsallis scheme seems to be one for which only the $q=1$ case represents maximum probability (minimal information). It is seen that $\sum_i p_i$ power q differs from $\sum_i p_i = 1$, suggesting that because the latter is used in Tsallis entropy, the normalization is a key

feature. To allow Sum over i p_i^q to become Shannon's entropy for $q=1$, one may write, as is well-known:

$$\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q) \quad ((6))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue, as in Part I, that Tsallis entropy is not linked with the usual maximum probability (minimum information), considered an essential idea of statistical mechanics, and suggest that this is because one has two sets of probabilities: p_i and p_i^q , and only the first is normalized. Thus, one cannot simply call p_i^q a new probability which should be maximized according to ((3)) and ((5)). As a result, one deliberately establishes a scheme ((6)) which yields maximum probability only for $q=1$ and deviates from it in a prescribed way otherwise, breaking from the minimal information scheme. The key feature is then whether this feature of non-minimal information appears in nature.